

12. INTERNATIONAL EUROPEAN CONGRESS ON ADVANCED STUDIES IN BASIC SCIENCES

DESIGN OF MICROCONTROLLER-BASED RESONANCE MONITORING SYSTEM FOR LLC TYPE MEDIUM FREQUENCY INVERTER

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ABSTRACT

Resonant inverters are widely chosen for their low switching losses and high efficiency, but maintaining peak performance remains challenging under varying load conditions. This study presents a microcontroller-based resonance monitoring system design to overcome the limitations of traditional LLC inverters, which typically rely on fixed control schemes or hardware-only solutions with limited dynamic response. The designed system is specifically adapted for a 10 kW, 10 kHz LLC resonant inverter used in induction heating applications. A series-resonant topology is employed, in which an inductively coupled voltage-source inverter drives the LLC tank to maximize current transfer while preserving a straightforward control structure, high power density and efficient thermal management. A full-bridge PWM stage using IGBTs is then synchronized to the resonant inductor's zero-current crossings, thus achieving Zero-Current Switching. This arrangement makes it possible to track the resonant frequency continuously: an ARM-based STM32G484CE microcontroller measures the tank response, detects resonance and adjusts the switching frequency in real time. Experimental results show the system responds rapidly to load transients and maintains a tracking error between $\pm 1\%$ and $\pm 0.5\%$. Keeping the operating frequency close to resonance reduces switching and conduction losses, significantly expanding the inverter's high-efficiency range.

Keywords: Resonance Tracking, Induction Heating, LLC Resonant Inverter.

1. INTRODUCTION

In systems requiring industrial power applications, Inductor-Inductor-Capacitor (LLC) type resonant inverters provide increasing efficiency, reliability and electromagnetic compatibility criteria, high efficiency and low electromagnetic interference advantages and are widely used in power electronics applications (Houam et al., 2022) . As a result of advantages such as zero voltage switching (ZVS) and zero current switching (ZCS), LLC resonant structures reduce the thermal stress of semiconductor switching elements while suppressing the electromagnetic interference (EMI) level (Chen, 2025).

Furthermore, this type of inverters are frequently used in power electronics systems because they offer advantages such as reducing switching losses in high and medium power electronic systems, the ability to operate at high efficiency with soft switching, and increasing system reliability (Chandrasekar & Babu, 2016). However, in order for LLC resonant inverters to operate in the efficient range, the condition is that the system operates at the resonant frequency. If the system achieves the resonant frequency at an optimal level, it affects the system efficiency to the extent that it does. The resonant frequency is determined by the inductance and capacitance values used in the circuit and changes depending on the changes in the load and input conditions. However, this situation makes it difficult to operate at optimum efficiency because it has a resonant frequency that changes according to dynamic load conditions. Today, hardware-based control methods are still mostly used in existing LLC resonant inverter systems. However, these structures are insufficient to keep the system efficiency at an optimum level under variable load conditions due to their limited dynamic response capabilities. This causes the systems to be insufficient in applications requiring high performance (Brajdić, 2023). In this study, a 10 kW power capacity and approximately 10 kHz resonance frequency LLC inverter design is presented, which can respond quickly to dynamic load changes with a microprocessor-based control method, thus minimizing energy losses and at the same time increasing this efficient operating range. With this approach, unlike hardware-based control methods, an LLC resonant inverter system is proposed, in which both control flexibility and energy efficiency are increased and the dynamic limitations of hardware control methods are overcome. The aim of this study is to present an advanced solution in terms of high performance and efficiency in LLC type medium frequency inverter applications and to apply the developed algorithm to real-time control applications. As a result, this study presents a method to improve the performance of LLC resonant inverters in academic and industrial applications and contributes to the development of applications requiring high efficiency in the field of power electronics.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

LLC type resonant converters are frequently used in various fields such as electric vehicle charging stations, laptop adapters, LCD TV power supplies, battery chargers and photovoltaic systems, and are also highly preferred in high-efficiency applications (Zeng et al., 2020). Ensuring the efficient operation of LLC inverters is still a subject of study today, and a control algorithm is being developed to monitor the resonance frequency under various load scenarios, thus expanding the efficient operating range. In such applications, monitoring the resonance frequency is the main element to increase efficiency. In this context, changing the switching frequency appropriately is of critical importance. In this study, a comprehensive analysis of control algorithms for LLC inverters is presented (Park et al., 2020). Juan L. Bellido et al. In this study presented by , this control method, which combines current controlled variable inductor (Variable Inductor – VI) and phase shift (Phase Shift – PS) control strategies, aims to increase efficiency by offering a new approach for parallel connected LLC resonant inverters. This hybrid control method significantly reduces switching losses while maintaining resonant conditions and allowing inverters to operate at optimal efficiency over a wider load range (Bellido et al., 2024). Kumar and his colleagues, who studied the LLC resonant converter topology, tried to show that power quality can be improved by correcting the power factor and reducing harmonic distortions in a resonant system operating directly with AC input. This structure is compact and has less energy loss compared to two-stage conventional systems. Moreover, As a result of zero-voltage switching (ZVS), energy efficiency is maintained while high efficiency is achieved even in high-frequency operating conditions (Kumar et al., 2024). Similarly, another study highlights how LLC resonant inverters minimize switching losses and increase efficiency by utilizing zero-voltage switching (ZVS) and zero-current switching (ZCS) features (Beiranvand et al., 2011). The ZVS (Zero Voltage Switching) technique used to provide high efficiency in LLC resonant inverters is the subject of this study to protect the switching elements. The

"Phase Boundary Control" approach of Kranprakon et al. tries to reduce the ZVS loss especially in applications involving induction heating systems. Non-ZVS operating and input current issues that may arise from changes in duty cycle in fixed-frequency operating systems controlled using asymmetric duty cycle (ADC) modulation are addressed (Kranprakon et al., 2019). Jeong et al. Through the development of load adaptive modulation techniques, the study aims to maximize the performance of series-connected resonant inverters. Different vessel materials and properties cause changes in the resonant frequency and inverter behaviour in cases where traditional control strategies assume of constant load. As a result, the efficiency of both the system and the heating process decreases. This study examines in detail the potential advantages of the ability of induction heating systems to adapt to various materials (Jeong et al., 2022). This study is based on the electrical behaviour of LLC resonant inverters against dynamic load changes and the asymmetric voltage cancellation control developed to increase efficiency in induction heating systems. This approach is a study that dynamically analyses and corrects voltage asymmetries at the inverter output to overcome the limitations of traditional control methods. At the same time, this study reduces both power losses and provides stable control of material temperatures (Chudjuarjeen et al., 2009). Considering these studies, the medium frequency LLC type microcontroller-based resonance monitoring system to be developed within the scope of this project is presented as a study that can monitor the resonance frequency in real time and dynamically adjust the switching frequency. The aim of this study is to achieve high efficiency by reducing switching losses and saving energy.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the steps followed in the design and implementation of microcontroller-based resonance monitoring system for LLC type medium frequency inverter are discussed with theoretical and experimental details. In this study, it has 10kW output power and approximately 10kHz resonance frequency. The system is fed with 380V AC and 50Hz mains voltage at its input and it is converted into alternating signal (AC) through LLC resonance tank and transferred to induction coil. Each step is supported by theoretical analysis and practical application conditions are considered. This section is explained under 3 main headings: Hardware Design, Software Design and Simulation and Test Results.

3.1 Hardware Design

The hardware part consists of 3 parts: LLC circuit, full bridge inverter circuit and resonant monitor board.

3.1.1 LLC Circuit

In the design of an LLC resonant inverter, the correct selection of basic circuit elements such as resonant inductor (L_r), magnetizing inductance (L_m) and resonant capacitor (C_r) is of great importance in terms of ensuring operation at the desired resonant frequency and making energy transmission efficient. In this study, the resonant tank circuit consists of a 1.5mH resonant inductance (L_1), a 1.6 μ H magnetizing inductance (L_2) and a 0.22 μ F resonant capacitor (C). The resonant tank is fed with a square wave alternating signal generated by the full bridge inverter and the frequency-dependent dynamic response of the system is examined through this structure. Since the resonant frequency f_r has series connected resonant inductance and capacitance and parallel connected magnetizing inductance L_m in the circuit, the LLC topology theoretically has two different characteristic resonant frequencies. In order to provide efficient and stable operation, the switching frequency is usually selected between these two resonant frequencies. However, only one of them provides the targeted output characteristic. The developed control algorithm detects the target resonant frequency and performs real-time frequency tracking to ensure maximum current transfer. The equations used to determine the resonant frequencies are mathematically presented in Equations (1) and (2).

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{(L_1//L_2)C}} \quad (1)$$

$$f_2 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_1C}} \quad (2)$$

In these equations, the relationship between L_r and C_r should be considered. One parameter is kept constant, and the other parameter is calculated. In the parameter calculation, attention should be paid to the frequency being generally close to the targeted frequency. Another factor to be considered is the quality factor, which expresses the sharpness and efficiency of the resonant circuit. A high Q value provides a sharper resonance but narrows the operating frequency range. The mathematical representation of the quality factor in the LLC resonant circuit is shown in equation (3).

$$Q = \frac{1}{R} \sqrt{\frac{L_r}{C_r}} = \frac{w_r L_r}{R} \quad (3)$$

R is the equivalent resistance reflected to the load and directly affects the efficiency and controllability of the circuit.

In the LLC topology, the magnetizing inductance L_m is connected in parallel with the circuit and this parameter affects the dynamic characteristics of the circuit. The ratio used to determine the relationship between the magnetizing inductance and the resonant inductance is given in equation (4).

$$k = \frac{L_m}{L_r} \quad (4)$$

This ratio is usually chosen between 3 and 10. A large k value widens the ZVS (zero voltage switching) range but can make output voltage regulation difficult. Therefore, the k value should be selected according to the response of the system.

Finally, the equivalent resistance R_{eq} can be calculated by considering the output power P_{out} and the load characteristics. In this way, it is used to determine other parameters in the circuit and is calculated with the formula in equation (5).

$$R_{eq} = \frac{V_{out}^2}{P_{out}} \quad (5)$$

As a result, the alternating signal generated at the output of the resonant tank is induced and creates a magnetic field on it, which is transferred to the coil by changing with time. Figure 1 shows a simplified simulation of the LLC resonant tank implemented in LTspice (LTspice Information Center | Analog Devices, 1999).

Figure 1. Simplified LLC Inverter Circuit Simulation in LTSpice.

3.1.2 Full Bridge Inverter

Inverters are one of the basic switching structures used to convert direct voltage (DC) sources into alternating voltage (AC) signals. The full bridge structure, which is widely used among inverter topologies, offers high power capacity by virtue of its symmetrical design and allows precise output control with PWM techniques. This structure consists of 4 power switching elements and operates with the cross-triggering method. The full bridge topology used in LLC type resonant inverters feeds the resonant tank circuit by converting the rectified DC voltage into a square wave form. Since this structure is designed to operate at the resonant frequency, it provides the advantage of providing zero voltage switching (ZVS) conditions. In this way, switching losses are minimized, thermal loads in the system are reduced and overall energy efficiency is increased. In this study, FUJI ELECTRIC's 2MBI300HJ-120-50 IGBT modules (2MBI300HJ-120-50 | Fuji Electric, 2010) with 1200V blocking voltage were used as given in Figure 2. These elements ensure safe operation of the system when used in this study by virtue of their 1200V blocking voltage and high current carrying capacity. It is not possible to drive these high-power IGBTs directly with the microcontroller due to their low voltage and current values. For this reason, VLA502-01R model power driver modules were used between the microcontroller and the IGBTs, shown in Figure 3. By virtue of their features such as opto-isolator and high current output, these drivers provide both isolation and drive the IGBT with appropriate voltage and current levels. The simulation image of the full bridge structure used in this study is given in Figure 4.

Figure 2. 2MBI300HJ-120-50 IGBT Modules.

Figure 3. VLA502-01R Model Power Driver Modules.

Figure 4. Full Bridge Switching Circuit Simulation in LTSpice.

3.1.3 Resonant Monitor Board

To measure the input voltage and current from the LLC resonant inverter board, the analog signals received from the V-IN and I-IN terminals are first suppressed by RC filters and protection diodes and then converted to digital by high-speed LM319N comparators (LM319-N - TI.Com, 1970). To suppress noise at the output, the signals passing through the Schmitt trigger and filter networks are synchronized to the processor clock by CD4013 flip-flops (CD4013B - TI.Com, 1970) and converted to clean-edge digital pulses. Some operations can be enabled or disabled when not needed with jumpers on the board. Some integrated circuits used are shown in Figures 5, 6 and 7.

Figure 5. CMOS Dual D-Type Flip-Flop.

Figure 6. CMOS Hex Schmitt-Trigger Inverters (CD40106B - TI.Com, 1970)

Figure 7. High Speed Dual Comparator

Finally, the digital signals that can be monitored from the test points allocated for each channel allow us to observe the application stages step by step. They are transmitted to the GPIO pins of the microcontroller via the J5 connector. Thus, the system voltage and current values are accurately digitized and transferred to the MCU; control and protection algorithms are run in real time. The schematic view of the board is given in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Resonant Monitor Board Schematic.

3.2 Software

In this study, the software architecture was designed in the STM32CubeIDE development environment using the STM32G474 microcontroller from STMicroelectronics (Figure 9, Figure 10).

Figure 9. STM32CubeIDE Programming Environment (STM32CubeIDE - STMicroelectronics, 2019).

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Figure 10. STM32G474RET6 Microprocessor (STM32G474RE - STMicroelectronics, 2019).

In the software section, the software completed the configuration of the ADC, TIM, DMA and GPIO units and enabled the hardware layer to ensure interaction between the hardware-software layers. The data flow received from the V-IN, I-IN and V-TANK signal lines on the circuit is collected in real time at the specified sampling frequency. After the data collection process, the resonance tracking algorithm is activated using interrupt functions to monitor the frequency of the I-IN and V-TANK signals. This architectural structure allows time-critical frequency analysis operations to be performed without delay. The resonance condition is analyzed via the I-IN (input current) and V-TANK (tank voltage) signals. The algorithm dynamically adjusts the PWM driver signals by taking the resonance frequency carried by the I-IN channel as a reference and ensures the synchronous operation of the I-IN and V-TANK channels. To minimize switching losses, the rising and falling edges of the PWM signal are optimized to support zero voltage switching (ZVS) conditions. The protection mechanisms disable the PWM output when the specified threshold values are exceeded and the system switches to safe mode and reports the fault condition. The general flow diagram of the developed control algorithm is presented in detail in Figure 11. This diagram shows the relationship between data acquisition, analysis, control signal generation and protection states and reveals the software structure of the system.

Figure 11. Dynamic Resonance Tracking Algorithm Flow Chart

3.3 Simulation and Test Results

The results of the simulations performed in Matlab/Simulink (Simulink - Simulation and Model-Based Design - MATLAB, 1990) and LTSpice environments, shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13 respectively, are presented in Figures 14–16. The Matlab/Simulink results are shown in Figure 14; the gate driver signals are in yellow and red colors, and the yellow waveform represents the induction coil output voltage. The results of the LTSpice simulation are given in Figure 15 and Figure 16; Figure 15 shows the PWM signals generated by the full-bridge inverter and the output voltage at the induction coil, and Figure 16 shows the details of the gate signals. Figure 17 shows an image of the real operating environment of the system. In this figure, the system modules are clearly visible. Finally, Figure 18 shows 2 figures. These figures show the oscilloscope images of the system's responses to the 2 resonance frequencies mentioned above.

Figure 12. System Simulation in Matlab/Simulink.

Figure 13. System Simulation in LTSpice.

Figure 14. Matlab/Simulink Gate Signals and Output Voltage on Induction Coil.

Figure 15. PWM Signals Generated by the Full-Bridge Inverter and the Output Voltage on the Induction Coil in LTSpice.

Figure 16. Gate signals in LTSpice.

Figure 17. Test Environment of the System.

Figure 18. System Response at Two Different Resonance.

4. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The developed system has the sensitivity to track the resonance frequency within the range of ± 0.2 kHz, and thus, energy efficiency above 95% has been achieved. As a result of the thermal analyses performed, it has been revealed that the thermal losses in semiconductor components have been reduced by approximately 10% by virtue of this control method. The system offers a wider operating range

compared to traditional methods operating with a fixed frequency and can also maintain stable operation under different load conditions. In this respect, it provides a significant advantage for applications requiring high efficiency. In further studies, it is aimed to further develop adaptive control by integrating artificial intelligence-based frequency estimation algorithms into the system.

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